

Green-Digital Transition in Municipal Waste Management: Ethnographic Perspective on 'Smart' Waste Monitoring and Management System

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Abstract:

This paper critically examines the Waste Monitoring and Management System (WMMS) implemented in several Polish cities as part of the green-digital transition. Positioned as a tool to advance green and digital transformation in waste management, WMMS promises to reduce environmental impact, improve recycling levels, and optimize waste collection. However, through ethnographic research, including 25 in-depth interviews and participant observations, the study reveals key discrepancies between these promises and the system's real-world outcomes. Rather than delivering environmental benefits, WMMS reinforces private sector control over municipal infrastructures, increases energy consumption due to extended data storage, and exacerbates issues of surveillance and data misrepresentation. These findings suggest that, despite the green-digital narrative, technologies like WMMS risk diverting attention from core environmental challenges by reducing complex ecological problems to technical solutions. The research underscores the need for more integrated approaches that

balance technological innovation with local realities to achieve meaningful progress in green policy.

Keywords:

Green-digital transition, smart waste management, green policy, digital transformation, ethnographic study, critical data studies, recycling, critical infrastructure studies

1. Introduction

In efforts to mitigate the impacts of the climate crisis, cities worldwide seek advanced technologies to handle increasing amounts of urban waste. New waste management strategies typically focus on the collection, sorting, recycling, and monitoring of waste (Olawade et al., 2024). Technologies such as smart bins, recycling robots, and automated sorting systems are believed to enhance these processes (Sharma & Vaid 2021). New discourses on waste management highlight potential benefits of technological solutions (Mukherjee et al., 2021). In fact, Morozov (2013) calls the phenomenon of promoting the positive aspects of technology the “technological solutionism”. Supported by green and digital transformation policies, the affirmative discourse claims that “smart”¹ waste management technologies are the key to reducing the environmental impact of waste and improving quality of life in cities (Czekala et al., 2023). It assembles a vision of a future where advanced solutions benefit both the environment and communities by reducing CO2 emissions, optimizing logistics, and increasing citizen engagement in recycling (Esmailian et al., 2018; 2023; Szpilko et al., 2023), “crafting the promise of technological fixes for social problems” (Mager & Katzenbach, 2021). Faced with this inspiring narrative, it becomes essential to understand how these technologies work, what they change about waste management routines and what the social and political implications of applying smart waste management are.

This work presents the results of an ethnographic study on the functioning of a new municipal waste monitoring system implemented in several Polish cities- the Waste Monitoring and Management System (WMMS). WMMS is analyzed as an example of “smart” waste management, critically reflected upon within the framework of waste anthropology (Drackner 2005; Offenhuber 2017; Lima 2023). The technology is situated within the context of the green-digital transformation of waste management systems. In the context of WMMS, waste in is not

¹ SMART is an acronym for Self-Monitoring Analysis and Reporting Technology (Singer 2020).

only viewed as an environmental or technological issue but it is also a key element in studying policies at the European, national and local levels.

The aim of this research is to critically analyze the functioning of the Waste Monitoring and Management System (WMMS) within the context of the green-digital transformation of waste management. The study seeks to understand how these technologies influence local waste management strategies, shaped by European Union policies, national frameworks, and the political discourse surrounding the Green Deal. By examining the discrepancies between the promises of WMMS and its real-world outcomes, the research reveals how different levels of policy impact local waste management practices and explores the social and ecological consequences of this technological implementation.

2. Critical Theoretical Framework for Waste Datafication and Digital Infrastructures

The article employs three theoretical approaches. The first, science and technology studies, posits that waste does not exist in a vacuum but is the result of social, technical, and institutional practices (Liboiron 2013). Waste, often seen as neutral, is the product of relationships between technology, society, and institutions.

The second approach, critical infrastructure studies, analyzes the WMMS infrastructure not only as a technical tool but also as a form of power that shapes social order and affects the relationships between citizens and the state (Larkin 2013). This approach highlights the role of invisible technologies in regulating daily life.

The third approach, critical data studies (Gitelman & Jackson 2013; Iliadis & Russo 2016), examines how the digitization of waste management affects everyday practices, what benefits and challenges arise from it, and what issues emerge in the context of the green-digital transformation. Datafication, which involves turning aspects of life into digital data (van Dijck 2014), is not only about the digitization of information but also about creating new forms of data from previously unquantified processes (Kitchin 2014).

In the context of waste, datafication means transforming both physical waste and related resident behaviors into digital data. This data, collected by smart containers equipped with cameras, sensors, and weighing systems, includes information on the quantity, type, and method of waste segregation. The goal of this process is to monitor, analyze, and optimize waste management. As a result, so-called digital twins – virtual representations of waste – are created. The process supports political decision-making and optimization of waste management

activities. Digital twins are part of a broader digital transformation promoted by the European Union under the *Digital Decade* initiative (EC, 2004). However, datafication brings challenges such as resident surveillance and the risk of errors in data recording and analysis.

Flensburg and Lomborg (2023) note that research on datafication rarely combines empirical analyses of infrastructure and technological processes. In response to this gap, my research provides an empirical examination of waste management policies and practices, focusing on the tensions between the promises of digital waste management technologies and their real-world implementation. By critically analysing these discrepancies, this study explores how digital infrastructures – using WMMS as a case study – both shape and are shaped by political narratives and local practices, ultimately questioning the effectiveness of green-digital policies in achieving their declared goals.

These theoretical perspectives guide the analysis of WMMS by revealing how infrastructures operate both as material and digital systems that shape social relations, governance, and everyday waste management practices. Critical infrastructure studies help illuminate how WMMS, as a technological system, becomes visible through failures and disruptions, while critical data studies provide insight into how datafication reconfigures urban waste governance, creating tensions between digital promises and their material realities.

3. Methods: Ethnographic Study of Waste Technology

To investigate the WMMS system, I employed an ethnographic method, similar approach to other researchers working with waste including Singer (2020) and Drackner (2005). Drackner (2005), in his research on waste in Peru, demonstrated that different social groups perceive waste as a threat, an aesthetic problem, or a resource. Similarly, the WMMS ethnography captured subjective perceptions of waste, providing crucial socio-cultural context that the technology alone cannot account for. Ethnographic methods like participant observation and qualitative interviewing allowed for a deeper understanding of the everyday functioning of WMMS, the associated practices, and the interactions in offices as well as in field settings such as waste management facilities, housing estates, and locations where WMMS containers are deployed.

In addition to ethnographic fieldwork, I conducted a policy analysis of key European Union documents that frame the green-digital transition in waste management. The selection of policy documents was based on their direct relevance to WMMS implementation and the promises of smart waste technologies. These included the European Green Deal (2019), which

establishes the broader political framework for the twin transition, the Circular Economy Action Plan (2015) and Directive (EU) 2018/851, which define recycling targets and waste monitoring requirements, as well as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (2016/679), which sets legal constraints on data collection and retention in digital waste infrastructures. The analysis focused on contrasting these policy objectives with empirical findings, highlighting discrepancies between political narratives and the real-world outcomes of WMMS implementation. This policy analysis complemented the ethnographic study by situating local experiences of WMMS within the broader regulatory framework, allowing for a multi-scalar understanding of waste governance.

A total of 25 in-depth interviews with municipal waste management stakeholders took place between May 2023 and September 2024: four with employees of the company responsible for the development of WMMS, eight with representatives from Waste Management Departments, three interviews with Polish waste management experts. Additionally, 10 conversational interviews (Rubin & Rubin, 2011) with staff from waste collection companies and housing estate administrations. These interviews provided diverse perspectives on the functioning of the system.

Participant observations took place in various environments—at municipal representative conferences, in the headquarters of the technology company, in the offices of housing estate administrations, and municipal offices—to better understand the practical operation of WMMS. Field notes were taken throughout these observations to capture detailed insights. Additionally, observations were made at six WMMS container locations in two cities, as well as spontaneous conversations with residents using the system. I also accompanied municipal employees during waste segregation inspections, which provided additional insights into the system's practical functioning.

All information was collected solely for scientific purposes, in accordance with personal data protection requirements, and the study was approved by the Ethics Committee of the Institute of Philosophy and Sociology at the Polish Academy of Sciences. All identifying data were anonymized. The interview recordings and field notes were secured and processed using MAXQDA software, ensuring the confidentiality and integrity of the study.

4. Promises of the Green-Digital Transition in Waste Management in Europe

The European Green Deal's (EC, 2019) call for "twin transition" emphasizes the joint effort to make the European economy more sustainable and modern (Muench et al. 2022: 7). "Twin transition" is guided by integration of environmental and digital goals, which already appeared in the "smart, sustainable, and inclusive growth" narrative as early as 2010 (Kovacic et al. 2024: 5). The key promises of the green-digital transformation shaping public perceptions of modern "smart" urban management solutions in Europe's waste management are based on the concept of the smart city as a sociotechnical imaginary. Digital-green promises are part of the narrative promoting smart urbanism as a solution to urban crises and the pathway to sustainable future (Sadowski & Bendor, 2018). These imaginaries do not emerge in a vacuum; rather, they are shaped by policy agendas, industry narratives, and market driven logics that influence how digital infrastructures are conceptualized and implemented (Mager & Katzenbach, 2021). Following Mager & Katzenbach (2021), these imaginaries are not only multiple and contested but also commodified, as digital technologies become embedded in governance frameworks and positioned as inevitable solutions to societal challenges. This process aligns with the broader trends of datafication and digital governance, where technologies are framed as neutral tools despite their embedded political and economic dimensions. These premises are central to the analysis of WMMS. They fit within the framework of the "twin transition", which integrates the goals of green and digital transformation (Kovacic et al. 2024; Rehman et al. 2023).

While the twin transition encompasses a wide array of objectives, including sustainable urban mobility, and improved energy efficiency in buildings, the three promises analysed here — energy savings, increased recycling levels, and dynamic waste collection — have been selected for their direct relevance to the WMMS system and their central role in shaping green digital expectations in urban waste management.

4.1 First Green-Digital Promise: Reducing Energy Consumption

The first key promise of the green-digital transformation is reducing energy consumption. Smart technologies, such as waste monitoring systems, require data storage in the cloud, which leads to high energy demand, especially in data centers. Data storage is one of the most energy-intensive aspects of the digital transformation, creating tensions between sustainability goals and increasing energy usage. To address this, it has been promised that

digital technologies will consume less energy than they are capable of saving (EC, n.d.). The European Data Strategy highlights the need for sustainable data collection and processing, drawing attention to energy issues in the context of digital transformation. Under the European Green Deal, the EU has committed to building climate-neutral and energy-efficient data centers, the so-called “green cloud and data centers” (EC, 2022). Reducing data retention time is a key element of this promise, aiming to improve energy efficiency.

4.2 Second Green-Digital promise: Enhancing Circular Economy

The second promise of the green-digital transformation is the development of a circular economy, aimed at maximizing resource use, which ‘would see nothing discarded and everything reused’ (O’Neill, 2019: 2). This model, referred to by Mah (2021) as “future proofing capitalism”, combines economic and environmental benefits, supporting economic growth while minimizing the exploitation of natural resources. The EU actively supports this model, aiming to mitigate raw material shortages by using materials already present in the economy (Winans et al., 2017). The Circular Economy Action Plan of 2015, developed in Directive (EU) 2018/851, sets recycling levels: 55% by 2025, 60% by 2030, and 65% by 2035.

Smart waste management technologies, such as WMMS, are promoted as “the solution capable of driving the necessary changes in recycling levels.” These technologies are framed as essential components of circular economy strategies, promising precise waste tracking, improved segregation, and more efficient recycling processes. For instance, in Polish municipalities, pilot projects implementing WMMS systems have reportedly achieved up to an 80% improvement in selective waste collection, according to company representatives, through digital monitoring and the use of QR-code-enabled waste tracking. By integrating data collection and monitoring throughout waste management processes, these systems aim to optimize resource flows and minimize waste mismanagement. Offenhuber (2017: 11) argues that the full realization of the circular economy requires extensive data collection infrastructure throughout the product lifecycle, from production to disposal.

4.3 Third Green-Digital Promise: Reducing Emissions and Pollution

The third promise of the green-digital transformation concerns reducing emissions and pollution through optimizing urban waste management processes. The Green Deal emphasizes the key role of smart technologies in achieving climate neutrality by 2050. An example of such solutions is dynamic waste management systems that monitor container fill levels and optimize collection routes to reduce emissions and pollution associated with transportation (EGDC,

2024). Directive 2008/98/EC obliges member states to minimize environmental impact and maximize resource efficiency, which includes optimizing waste collection.

All these promises form the foundation of the green-digital transformation narrative and will be analysed in the context of the implementation of the WMMS system, as discussed in the following sections of the article.

5. Green-Digital Manifestations in the Waste Monitoring and Management System

This section presents the key findings of the research on WMMS, analyzing the extent to which current data retention practices reflect the promise of energy savings. The study also focuses on whether WMMS supports achieving the recycling levels required by the EU and how it contributes to emission reductions and sustainable waste management.

The introduction of WMMS marked an important moment in the development of urban infrastructure, which can be described as an infrastructural event (Carse, 2017) – a transformative shift that made previously mundane and traditional waste containers suddenly visible as active elements of the urban landscape. The implementation of WMMS redefined waste disposal practices, embedding technological mediation in everyday routines and prompting public debate. These transformations were particularly evident in moments of initial resistance, as some residents and local media outlets raised concerns about the surveillance aspects of the system and the challenges of adapting to new waste disposal procedures.

This transformation was particularly noticeable in a medium-sized city (50,000 inhabitants), where the introduction of these more complex devices visibly altered the urban landscape. The deployment of WMMS also required residents to adapt their everyday routines, such as scanning QR codes when disposing of waste. These adjustments profoundly changed daily waste disposal practices, embedding residents into a more closely monitored and regulated system.

In the context of WMMS, technological failures—such as problems with opening containers, system crashes, and the need for component replacements—align more closely with the concept of infrastructural in/visibility (Star & Ruhleder, 1996). As Star and Ruhleder (1996) argue, infrastructure typically remains unnoticed until it fails, at which point its material and political dimensions come to the fore. These breakdowns temporarily expose the technological fragility of WMMS, making its dependencies visible to both residents and municipal workers.

WMMS introduced several technological solutions, including weighing systems, QR code readers, automatic lids, monitoring cameras, and fill-level sensors, all designed to collect and process waste-related data. However, during the initial phase of implementation, the technology faced significant technical problems, as acknowledged by the housing administration representative: “At the beginning, WMMS would crash, we had problems opening the containers, and technical component replacements were needed”. These technical failures made the infrastructure visible, reminding residents of its presence and underscoring the dependence of the system on continuous technological reliability.

While the implementation of WMMS can be understood as an infrastructural event (Carse, 2017), its subsequent technological failures align with the concept of infrastructural in/visibility (Star & Ruhleder, 1996), exposing the dependencies and fragility of the system. Building on the concept of infrastructural visibility (Star & Ruhleder, 1996), the WMMS case highlights two interconnected dimensions of infrastructural exposure: physical and digital. While physical disruptions—such as malfunctioning containers or the need for component replacements—draw attention to the material fragility of the waste containers, they also reveal a growing dependence on digital infrastructure. This dependence is exemplified by the role of WMMS technology in the datafication of waste. With sensors installed in “smart” containers, the system monitors parameters such as material type, weight, time, and location of waste disposal. This data forms the basis for creating “digital twins,” which enable precise tracking of the waste life cycle, resident habits, and optimization of waste collection. Through this process, the WMMS transforms waste management practices, integrating both physical and digital elements into a cohesive, yet often fragile, infrastructural system.

These infrastructural transformations underpin the green-digital promises linked to the WMMS system, as outlined in Table 1. The table is positioned here to provide a structured overview of these promises before delving into their empirical manifestations. This allows the reader to grasp the key elements of the analysis beforehand, ensuring a clearer understanding of how the green-digital transition unfolds in practice. This table illustrates the link between the green-digital transformation promises, stakeholders, types of data collected, European Union policies, and the real-world manifestations and outcomes of these promises in the context of the WMMS system. These promises, primarily formulated by the private technology company, concern data retention periods, increased recycling levels, and dynamic waste collection. The key stakeholders include residents, municipalities, and waste disposal companies, all of whom are involved in fulfilling these promises through interactions with data collected by WMMS, such as the weight, type of waste, and container fill levels. Although these promises align with

Green-digital promises	Stakeholders	Data types	EU policies	Green-digital manifestations	Hidden effects of unfulfilled green-digital promises
Data should be stored for 7 days	Residents	Monitoring recordings	The General Data Protection Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2016/679)	Extended retention of monitoring data beyond legal limits, leading to privacy concerns	Strengthening private power over municipalities and citizens
Increase recycling levels	Municipalities	Waste weight	Directive (EU) 2018/851 (Article 11)	Misrepresentation of recycling data due to waste diversion and incomplete data tracking	Distraction from core issues
Dynamic waste collection	Waste disposal company staff	Container fill levels	Directive 2008/98/EC	Inefficient dynamic waste collection leading to increased operational costs and emissions	Reducing challenges to technical problems

Table 1. Overview of Green-Digital Promises, Stakeholders, Data Types, EU Policies, and Real-World Outcomes in the WMMS System

EU policies – the Regulation (EU) 2016/679, Directive 2018/851, and Directive 2008/98/EC – the actual manifestations of these promises often deviate from expectations, leading to hidden effects.

5.1 Manifestation of First Green-Digital Promise: Urban Surveillance and Extended Lifespan of Digital Data

In this section, I analyse how the first promise of the green-digital transformation, aimed at reducing energy consumption, is realized through the functioning of the WMMS system. Despite the declared goal of saving energy, WMMS technology operates as a form of “urban surveillance technology” (Sadowski, Pasquale 2015: 9), where residents become the object of monitoring and control. The introduction of the system sparked controversy as many residents perceived it as a form of excessive surveillance. According to interviews with municipal employees, even before implementation residents feared that WMMS would track what waste they were disposing of, potentially revealing their shopping habits and dietary preferences, leading to a loss of privacy.

Residents pointed out that now it will be known what they throw away. The anonymity they had until now was safe. They said that we will now know, among other things, what they eat, what they buy, and so on; that we are attacking them, that we want to surveil them, that we are doing this to spite them.

Despite these concerns, the system was implemented, and its presence became noticeable in residents' daily lives. The WMMS system not only monitors the quantity and type

of waste disposed of but also uses cameras to record every deviation from established norms, such as leaving waste outside the container. The footage is analyzed in real-time by algorithms that trigger alarms, allowing for immediate intervention by municipal services. As reported by one of the interviewed employees responsible for monitoring, the system functions efficiently: “The monitoring system automatically sends an alarm 20 seconds after detecting a violation, such as a bag left under the bin. The system immediately informs the manager, who takes action, often calling the municipal police”.

The monitoring data is stored in the cloud by the company managing WMMS, which draws parallels to the concept of a “smart prison” (Kaun, Stiernstedt 2020).

Drawing on this analogy, the WMMS system mirrors aspects of the “smart prison” through its pervasive surveillance of residents’ waste disposal practices. Similar to the way prison technologies track inmate behavior, WMMS monitors residents by collecting detailed data on the time, type, and quantity of waste they dispose of. These technologies do not merely passively collect data but actively analyze it in real-time, triggering alerts and enabling predictive measures to pre-empt deviations from established waste disposal norms. This constant monitoring and data retention raise questions about privacy and data security, particularly when it comes to the length of time monitoring data is stored. However, while the surveillance logic of WMMS has similarities to the “smart prison”, it is important to acknowledge its limitations. Unlike prisoners, who are under continuous surveillance with no opt-out option, residents can still evade WMMS monitoring by discarding waste in unmonitored locations. This distinction highlights the partial and uneven nature of WMMS surveillance, which, while extensive, does not fully enclose residents within a system of total control.

The controversy concerning the application of monitoring solutions in the WMMS system involves the length of time the monitoring data is stored. According to regulations, monitoring recordings should be kept for a maximum of seven days unless they serve as evidence in legal proceedings. This information is displayed on the containers:

In accordance with Article 13, paragraphs 1 and 2 of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (EU) 2016/679, monitoring records will be stored depending on the amount of recorded data – until the data is overwritten, no longer than seven days from the day of recording. In cases where the recording serves as evidence in legal proceedings or the Administrator has obtained legal notice of the conclusion of the proceedings, the recordings containing personal data will be destroyed after this period.

However, participant observation at the municipal office, as well as visits to the technology company and housing cooperative administration, revealed that the recordings are stored for up to a year. Thus, the data retention period exceeds the legally prescribed seven

days, which surpasses the declared “lifespan” of these digital twins. When asked about the retention period, head of the municipal waste management department responded:

Honestly, we still have recordings from last year. I don't know about earlier, because I haven't checked recently, but I was looking for something from around July or August of last year, and the recordings were there. And when I go back, I'll check out of curiosity if I can go all the way back to the beginning. No one from the WMMS company has ever told me if [the data retention] has any kind of warranty period.

The WMMS system retains data for significantly longer than 7 days, in clear violation of EU data protection regulations. The practice also raises concerns regarding compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) of the European Commission. GDPR was particularly intended to be “an essential step to strengthen citizens' fundamental rights in the digital age and facilitate business by simplifying rules for companies in the Digital Single Market” (Mager & Katzenbach, 2021: 224). This WMMS data storage concerns mirror broader concern about systems that store and process vast amounts of personal data without the users' knowledge or consent (Lyon, 2014).

The extended retention of data and the prolonged “lifespan” of “digital twins” in the WMMS system, beyond the assumptions of the “green-digital promises,” create tensions between digital and environmental aspects of the transformation. The increased demand for storage space leads to higher energy consumption, contradicting the declared goal of energy savings. A system intended to support the green transition through ecological waste management becomes a source of unsustainable practices stemming from excessive data retention. EU recommendations for limiting data storage time in the cloud, aimed at saving energy, are not being followed, which in the long term contributes to environmental degradation. As a result, the energy savings declared by the European Commission are undermined by violations of regulations and non-compliance with the assumptions.

5.2 Manifestation of Second Green-Digital Promise: Data Misrepresentation and the Role of Human Intervention in Circular Waste Management

In this section, I analyse how the second promise of the green-digital transformation, concerning the increase in recycling levels, is realized in practice through the WMMS system. The system was designed as an infrastructure that collects data in line with EU policies, particularly Directive (EU) 2018/851 (Article 11), which sets specific recycling targets: 55% by 2025, 60% by 2030, and 65% by 2035. Failure to meet these targets results in serious

financial repercussions. In Poland, the financial burden from these repercussions fall on municipalities.

Afraid of financial penalties, many municipalities seek solutions in technological innovation. As one official explains:

We were actually looking for ways to increase recycling levels in the city. We all know there's an issue, and soon we face serious penalties for not meeting the standards. Then a company came forward offering us a waste management system.

EU standards directly influence the way waste management technologies, such as WMMS, are designed. This system analyzes the ratio of mixed waste to fractions such as plastic, paper, or glass. Electronic containers equipped with sensors and QR codes record the disposed waste, providing detailed data about its type and quantity. This data is then transmitted to the municipal app, allowing for the monitoring of waste and residents' behaviors within the framework of so-called dataveillance (Clarke 1988; Van Dijck 2014).

WMMS is promoted as technology that helps municipalities meet recycling targets and therefore reduces the risk of financial penalties. The company that developed WMMS technology stresses the system improves waste segregation, yielding tangible benefits in the context of EU regulations. In the spirit of “technological solutionism” (Morozov 2013), a company representative stated: “It’s a unique product that significantly improves this negative trend and also gives cities some defensive shield against the fines they are threatened with.”

In contrast to WMMS marketing, WMMS's effectiveness is not clear. Although WMMS was meant to support increased recycling levels, significant discrepancies between the principles of the technology and its actual functioning are apparent. For instance, the main concern is data inaccuracy that hampers the achievement of the intended recycling levels. This simply means, that despite the assumption, the “digital twins” of waste that WMMS generates do not reflect the actual content of the containers². Waste collection staff noticed that after the introduction of WMMS, the amount of waste in the monitored containers decreased by half, while the amount of waste in unmonitored bins increased. One reason for this situation is that residents, who wished to avoid being monitored, used traditional containers of neighboring buildings or street bins that are not part of the WMMS system. As waste that should be monitored disappears from the system. A “digital tween” is incomplete, which misleads conclusions about the effectiveness of segregation. As Jensen (2021) notes, the core of waste

² This aligns with my previous analysis of “waste data reflectivity”, where the Digital Urban Waste Tracking System (DUWTS) was shown to create distorted reflections of waste management processes, obscuring the true nature of the waste collected and complicating municipal decision-making (Strzelecka 2024).

monitoring solutions is to understand how waste circulates in social and physical systems. Ignoring these social aspects, as evidenced by WMMS, results in waste landing outside the system's control, significantly weakening its capacity to inform municipality decisions.

Another concern is that much of the waste deposited in “smart” containers is still not properly sorted. Recycling levels are calculated based on the ratio of mixed waste to other fractions such as plastic or glass. The WMMS technology assumes that the contents of a bag match the fraction marked on the QR code, but it does not verify the actual contents of the bags. Hence, amount waste in each container does not reflect the actual segregation.

In the end, while the system was intended to provide a modern smooth solution to waste recycling issues, it still requires human interventions – the so-called human-in-the-loop (Jones 2017) – to ensure proper functioning. Therefore, municipal employees play a crucial role in controlling waste segregation by opening the containers and manually checking the contents of the bags. One of the municipal employees reflected that him and his colleagues are part of the system’s infrastructure, overseeing the correctness of segregation and supporting the functioning of WMMS: “I, along with my colleague, go on inspections and check whether the segregation in the containers is done correctly.”

However, their work is not limited to overseeing the process – they open the containers, check the contents of the bags, and thus help improve recycling levels. Quite the opposite, another employee noted that “during inspections, [they] see what medications they use, some diapers, some papers, receipts. They are afraid of that surveillance.” Municipal employees became “embodied infrastructure” (Lima, 2023), essential for the proper functioning of the system. Their physical involvement is crucial, as also confirmed by the head of the waste management department:

As the owner of these nodes, obligated to control the accuracy of waste segregation, we conduct inspections. Our department employees go to the node. We have our access cards and can open the node. The inspection is carried out by manually pulling out a bag, opening it, checking what’s inside, how it looks, whether the fractions match, whether it was properly discarded. And on the bags, there should be stickers to open the nodes. The contents of the bag can be assigned to a specific household covered by the system.

During inspections, employees scan the QR codes on the bags and document the waste content by taking photos before and after opening the bag. In case of irregularities, the resident receives a notification in the app, and in extreme cases, higher waste collection fees may be imposed. As reported by my interviewees, over half of the bags contain unsorted waste, which is a significant problem, particularly when the waste is discarded without a QR code, making it

impossible to identify. My ethnographic observations revealed that many improperly sorted bags do not have any QR code markings.

Despite WMMS being promoted as a tool to improve recycling levels, the reality shows that the technology neither increases efficiency nor provides reliable data on segregation. The system merely simulates an improvement in recycling processes, failing to fully realize the green-digital promises. Tensions between digitization and ecological aspects of the transformation, as evidenced by WMMS, indicate that despite the promises, it is not clear that datafication delivers environmental benefits.

5.3 Manifestation of Third Green-Digital Promise: Inefficiencies of Dynamic Waste Collection and Its Environmental Impact

The final green-digital promise is about the reduction of emissions and pollution through dynamic waste collection. In theory, sensors that monitor the fill levels of containers should enable optimization of waste collection routes and schedules. The assumption is that precise real-time data will reduce unnecessary waste truck trips, thereby decreasing emissions and operational costs (Wang et al., 2021). In WMMS, dynamic waste collection relies on smart bins equipped with IoT sensors that monitor fill levels. These data, during their "data journey" (Bates et al., 2016), are sent to a central management system and then to applications used by waste collection companies. "Digital twins" of waste – virtual models – are created to indicate which containers need emptying. These dynamic digital models should improve waste collection management, enhance logistics, and reduce resource consumption. As Joss et al. (2019) point out, this optimization becomes a key element of smart city systems, supporting better management of urban infrastructure, including waste systems, which allows for more efficient planning and resource use.

Company representatives promoting the WMMS system assure that the dynamic waste collection solves the problem of unoptimized logistics, eliminating unnecessary waste truck trips, which is supposed to lead to reduced emissions and fuel consumption. They also claim this technology will generate logistical savings of 20-30%. However, findings reveal a different picture. Namely, instead of experiencing operational improvements, municipal employees complained about longer working hours: "You have to open everything, wait, and in the winter, you also have to clear snow from the containers." Traditional collection schedules are still in use because dynamic collection often turns out to be more time-consuming and generates higher operational costs for municipality, including fuel consumption or longer routes. Waste collection workers were sceptical about the dynamic waste collection model: "It won't work

(...) I will wear myself out (...) it's unfeasible (...) it would just be driving around in circles.” The dispatch manager especially concern about operational costs due to dynamic waste collection: “If you go to one container, it's illogical not to empty the others, even if they aren't full. Otherwise, we'd have to come back the next day, which wastes fuel and time.”

The reality of the WMMS system does not align with the promised benefits. Instead of reducing working hours and emissions, dynamic collection has proven to be more complicated and costly. WMMS was supposed to improve waste management at the municipal level; instead, it generates new problems and challenges. Ultimately, dynamic waste collection becomes an example of so-called „green-digital washing”, where new technologies lead to increased energy and resource consumption, failing to reduce environmental impacts.

6. Discussion: the Hidden Effects of Unfulfilled Green-Digital Promises in Waste Management

Research on WMMS revealed hidden effects stemming from unmet promises of green-digital transformation in waste management. Although these systems are promoted as tools supporting EU goals, ethnographic research identified discrepancies between their aims and reality. Instead of delivering environmental benefits, WMMS may produce unintended social consequences. This discussion highlights three main aspects: strengthening the power of private tech companies, diverting attention from the issue of waste overproduction, and reducing complex environmental challenges to technical problems.

6.1 Strengthening Private Power Over Municipalities and Citizens

One of the key effects of implementing WMMS is the growing power of private tech companies. The system, developed and managed by a private company, reflects broader trend of urban digitalization where the private sector plays a dominant role in waste management (Kloppenburg et al., 2022). Data collection, often done without citizens' full consent, becomes a tool for commercialization and surveillance, aligned with the "logic of capital accumulation" (Sadowski, 2019). The data collected becomes a valuable resource for further exploitation, according to the “data imperative” (Fourcade & Healy, 2017).

Datafication of waste management transforms residents' everyday actions into digital data, reinforcing the power of tech companies (Kitchin et al., 2017). As systems like WMMS are funded by public money they further entangle municipalities with private suppliers. For instance, one municipality funded 90% of the system's cost through the Polski Ład (“Polish

Deal”) governmental program, investing over 5 million PLN. Although labelled a “pilot program”, municipalities become dependent on this technology, limiting future system choices.

Photography 2: Public Investment in Waste Management – The Polski Ład Programme's Financial Support for WMMS Implementation

The signing of contracts for WMMS creates infrastructural dependency between municipalities and companies, turning infrastructure into a tool of power (Larkin, 2013). Data stored on private servers deepens municipal reliance on specific technology providers. These contracts, typically lasting three years, enable companies to renegotiate terms in their favour, restricting municipal options. This kind of dependence leads to “lock-in effects”, where the adopted technology becomes hard to replace and reinforces “path dependence”, where past technological decisions dictate future choices (Arthur, 1989).

The lack of public debate before WMMS left no opportunity for residents to voice objections to data collection. This process aligns with the logic of “data extraction” (Sadowski, 2019), where citizens' data is collected and exploited for commercial purposes. Segura and Waisbord (2019) argue that urban datafication supports corporate interests by exploiting citizens' data, transforming them into “datafied subjects” used by private companies.

6.2 Distraction from Core Issues

WMMS distracts from key waste management challenges by creating the illusion of technological effectiveness, which does not lead to long-term ecological solutions. Tech companies promote these systems as environmental solutions, fitting into the narrative of technosolutionism (Morozov, 2013), but often generate profit without addressing real challenge (Heeks, 2018). WMMS does not address the waste overproduction but instead it complicates waste management by increasing reliance on digital and energy infrastructure (Fang et al., 2023; Kanungo, 2023). It provides a false sense of effectiveness, legitimizing existing structures without producing real results (Foster, 2012; Grunwald, 2018).

While indicators like recycling levels may suggest progress, they do not always reflect genuine environmental improvements. The digitalization of waste management reinforces the control of tech companies over environmental policies, sidelining real problems in favour of inconsistent technological solutions (Vezzoni, 2023). According to Turnhout et al. (2014) reliance on indicators—so-called measurementality—supports neoliberal environmental governance.

A key problem in Poland is the lack of implementation of Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) programs, as required by the EU (Strzelecka, 2024). Poland still fails to meet EU requirements, exposing a gap between national policies and EU regulations (Rzeczpospolita, 2024; Szopiński & Tarkowska-Losik). WMMS shifts responsibility onto residents, ignoring key issues such as the lack of EPR legislation.

Although WMMS theoretically supports the green and digital transition, it benefits from systemic issues like the lack of EPR implementation, which results from inconsistent public policies in waste management (Hird et al., 2014). This situation underscores the need for a critical view of technologies that exploit such inconsistencies without delivering genuine environmental benefits.

6.3 Reducing Challenges to Technical Problems

Technologies like WMMS simplify complex environmental challenges, reducing them to technical issues with a focus on data collection and analysis. Rather than solving environmental problems at their source, these systems focus on waste monitoring, limiting opportunities for sustainable development. Growing technological complexity pushes ecological issues to the background (Cardullo & Kitchin, 2019). For instance, dynamic waste collection, aimed at reducing emissions, is likely to increase energy consumption. This is because waste trucks make additional trips before their containers are full (Bates et al., 2016). The data collected may influence public policies, but its inaccuracy often leads to poor decisions, reinforcing existing problems rather than solving them.

Technologies like WMMS legitimize existing waste management structures by focusing on data collection and processing. However, as Kitchin (2014: 9) notes, “technological solutions on their own are not going to solve the deep-rooted structural problems in cities because they do not address their root causes. Rather, they only enable the more efficient management of the manifestations of those problems.” Mattern (2013) adds that big data urbanism’s assumption that all processes and activities can be accurately measured often leads to flawed decisions by city management. Therefore, as waste management digitalization progresses, it is essential to critically assess whether these technologies contribute to sustainability or merely perpetuate ineffective practices, maintaining the status quo of waste-related problems.

7. Conclusion

The study highlighted the role of technology in waste management, revealing tensions between green-digital transformation promises and the actual practices of different actors entangled in municipal waste governance. While promoted as a solution to environmental problems, WMMS also reflects a technocratic belief in technology's ability to address ecological issues. The system promised benefits like optimized waste collection and recycling monitoring. However, this research highlights a gap between these promises and reality. The implementation of WMMS functioned as an infrastructural event (Carse, 2017), momentarily making waste management infrastructure visible as it was introduced and contested. Yet, over time, its failures and inefficiencies became more apparent, aligning with Star and Ruhleder’s (1996) concept of infrastructural in/visibility. The system remained unnoticed until breakdowns—whether technical failures or contradictions in data management—brought its

fragility to the forefront. At the same time, the surveillance mechanisms embedded in WMMS, particularly its data retention policies, mirror aspects of the “smart prison” (Kaun & Stiernstedt, 2020), reinforcing power asymmetries between municipal authorities, residents, and private technology providers. Daily experiences of actors, from municipal employees to residents, reveal significant limitations. Waste collectors reported operational complications due to technical failures, while residents viewed the system as invasive, fearing surveillance of their waste habits. These experiences illustrate how a technology intended as an innovative solution instead generates new social tensions and discomfort.

The system’s impact on recycling was also questionable. Many residents avoided using WMMS-monitored containers, forcing municipalities to rely on manual checks, further highlighting distrust in the system’s effectiveness. Instead of reducing waste, the system sometimes exacerbated problems, such as unnecessary energy consumption for data storage. Consequently, rather than promoting sustainability, WMMS risks becoming an example of “greenwashing,” where technology serves more to enhance image than to drive real environmental progress.

In sum, WMMS, promoted as a tool to support circular economy principles, struggles to achieve its objectives. Misrepresented data and flawed waste monitoring create a false sense of efficiency, masking the absence of real recycling progress. Rather than relying solely on advanced technologies, achieving the three key promises of the green-digital transition examined in this study—energy savings, increased recycling levels, and dynamic waste collection—requires integrated approaches that account for both local conditions and global ecological challenges. Cutting-edge technologies cannot alone resolve complex waste management issues without proper regulatory and political support. Ethnographic insights into WMMS highlight the importance of daily interactions with technology, exposing its limitations and contradictions. To truly improve environmental outcomes and urban life, a re-evaluation of technology implementation policies is essential.

8. References

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